

Balancing AI Innovation and Privacy in Mental Health Therapy: A Case Study from Co-Opts

Primary Contributor: Kevin Flanagan Editors: Stuart Gillespie
Malvika Sharan

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A key barrier to data handling in mental health care is the lack of baseline measurements. Unlike physical health, where vitals such as temperature and blood pressure have provided objective data points for at least a century, existing mental health assessments tend to rely on self-reported and potentially highly subjective questionnaires. To address this thorny challenge, healthtech company [Co-Opts](#) is building a trans-diagnostic, pan-treatment intervention for mental health and therapy. Their motivation is to use AI for user empowerment, giving patients ownership of their data.

In this case study, founder Kevin Flanagan, an Expert-in-Residence in *The Turing Way* Practitioners Hub, describes Sylvie, a digital assistant-sized listening and analysis AI device. The case study also provides insights into their data governance framework that incorporates ethical considerations into their product.

Focus on Privacy and Usability

Sylvie is designed to capture data that passes between the clinician and the patient during a session. As a device physically placed in the therapy room, data includes conversations and vocal biomarkers, as well as periods of silence, emotional arcs, themes and topics covered, and information on the therapist’s clinical practice. Deploying AI and Machine Learning technologies responsibly in the context of therapy includes automated transcription, speaker identification, summarisation and topic extraction. It also integrates the use of Edge AI, the practice of running AI models locally on a physical device rather than relying on remote cloud computing.

“Empowering patients improves adherence, motivation and, ultimately, outcomes.”, says Kevin. However, therapy often has a built-in power imbalance in favour of the clinician. Mental health treatment also expects patients to remember and practice skills from therapy, but we know that stress impairs memory. We wouldn’t expect someone to remember every word of a medical professional, which is one of the reasons patients are often accompanied by someone when receiving a diagnosis related to their physical health, so why do we expect it in mental health? Sylvie assists users by making session content and analysis immediately and easily available.

“The basic function of Sylvie is to record, transcribe and summarise therapy sessions.”, he adds. “At the end of a session, the service user scans a QR code, and the data is transferred to both their device and the therapist’s device, such as a mobile phone. It is then deleted from Sylvie, with no cloud storage and no lingering records.”

The Ethical Challenges of Therapy Recording and Analysis

To establish more systematic measures for mental health conditions, an AI device needs to be designed to capture therapy session data in a contextualised and structured manner, while maintaining the anonymity of users. “The keyword here is ‘anonymised’. The therapy room is a sacred space,” says Kevin. “The biggest ethical dilemma is balancing innovation with privacy, and resolving that tension. Is the risk of gathering this data outweighed by the potential to finally establish real baselines in mental health? Anonymisation is a tricky business – it’s both a technical and a governance challenge.”

Co-Opt’s proposed therapy data collection and analysis system introduces several important ethical challenges that must be addressed to ensure privacy, fairness and trust. Those challenges and issues include:

- **Privacy and Data Sensitivity:** The system records and analyses highly personal therapy conversations and vocal biomarkers, making it one of the most sensitive forms of personal health data. Risks include unauthorised access, data breaches, and misuse of recorded conversations (even with anonymisation, voice patterns could potentially be used for re-identification).
- **Consent and Autonomy:** Genuine informed consent from both therapists and patients is paramount. Given the inherent power imbalance in therapy, patients may feel pressured to participate, fearing potential repercussions for opting out.
- **Data Governance and Control:** A clear governance framework is needed to define who can access the data, under what conditions, and for what purposes. Questions around data storage, deletion and ownership, whether it belongs to patients, therapists, the company or researchers, must also be addressed.
- **Algorithmic Bias and Fairness:** AI-driven analysis of speech patterns poses risks of bias, particularly if training data is not diverse. There is a need to ensure fair performance across different demographics and to prevent the reinforcement of existing mental healthcare disparities.
- **Balancing Individual and Collective Benefit:** A core ethical dilemma lies in balancing individual privacy with the collective benefits of improved mental health treatments. While creating standardised datasets could enhance therapy effectiveness, participation must be voluntary, and the benefits should be equitably distributed.
- **Professional Ethics and Clinical Safety:** The presence of recording devices in therapy rooms raises concerns about their impact on the therapeutic relationship and clinical effectiveness. Therapists have professional obligations to maintain confidentiality and uphold ethical standards.
- **Long-term Implications:** Beyond its immediate application, the long-term use of collected data poses ethical challenges. For example, future advances in AI and re-identification techniques may compromise anonymisation efforts, or changing social attitudes may increase the potential for commercial exploitation of therapy data.

- **Implementation and Oversight:** A structured, transparent and independent approach to oversight is crucial for ensuring ethical integrity. Continuous monitoring and evaluation processes should be established to address emerging risks.

Developing a Governance Framework for Ensuring Ethical Deployment

To tackle these varied challenges, Co-Opts is designing a dynamic, human-centred data governance framework alongside technical safeguards which, in tandem, allow for the benefits of structured mental health data collection while protecting the privacy and rights of patients. In this way, the company can achieve its mission of improving mental health outcomes through ethically sound, AI-driven solutions.

“We thought we had an ethics policy,” says Kevin, “until we took part in the [Digital Catapult’s Machine Intelligence Garage](#) and worked with experts to carry out an ethical deep-dive as part of the programme. We have since maintained a living, more comprehensive ethics and data governance document that acknowledges these issues require ongoing vigilance and adaptation.”

On the technical side, the company is exploring the use of Edge AI techniques to process data directly on the device rather than sending it to a central server. This means that AI-driven insights happen locally, ensuring sensitive therapy conversations never leave the user’s control and allowing models to improve through a federated system of devices (in effect, a ‘distributed supercomputer’). We also have an initial bias towards more deterministic models to improve user confidence rather than an AI everywhere, everything and all at once approach.

Kevin shares how this is a direct outcome of his participation in the Practitioners Hub: “We were introduced to the Turing-BridgeAI Independent Scientific Advisers, who recommended we explore Edge AI as a solution for Sylvie. We are now working with Professor Omer Rana and colleagues, experts in edge computing at Cardiff University, and colleagues to develop this proposal further.”

Engaging the user community in strengthening the governance framework

Sylvie is still in the early ‘minimum viable product’ stage of development, with the hardware nearly finalised and the software still evolving. The team is integrating two different speech-to-text models and various algorithms to refine analysis of the therapy sessions, alongside its work navigating the complex ethical and governance challenges. Ultimately, the goal is to deploy across the NHS and private practice.

To ensure that the user community can be part of developing the governance framework that meets their needs, Co-Opts intends to involve the following community engagement methods (but are not limited to):

- establishing an anonymisation oversight working group to monitor risks, evaluate new technologies and datasets, test the effectiveness of anonymisation processes, and develop response protocols for identified vulnerabilities
- continuous monitoring and risk assessment to identify emerging de-anonymisation techniques and re-identification risks
- active engagement with key stakeholders such as patient communities, clinical practitioners, and technology and ethics experts to ensure transparency and trust, and

that privacy concerns are addressed

- establishing a clear set of policies covering aspects including thresholds for action, decision-making criteria, risk assessment methods, documentation standards, and review cycles.

Next Stages for Product Development

Highlighting the next steps for Co-Opts in refining both the ethical and algorithmic aspects of Sylvie, Kevin says, “We’re trying to do a hard thing, in a hard place, in a hard way. Therapists may say they don’t want these devices in their rooms, but we find that if we can talk to them for 20 or 30 minutes about the product and its potential benefits, it’s like a Damascene conversion. Of course, we also need to get patient buy-in, and that may be even harder.

“But we think we can improve therapy outcomes by at least 10% and possibly by as much as 50% in the future across anxiety, depression, schizophrenia and more – That would be revolutionary.”

Key takeaways

- Sylvie, an AI-powered physical device by Co-Opts, records, transcribes, and summarises therapy sessions. Sylvie provides objective data in mental healthcare, offering a solution to address the lack of baseline measurements compared to physical health.
- Co-Opts aims to empower patients by giving them ownership of their therapy session data, improving patient engagement and outcomes. Their solution enables data transfer to patients' and therapists' devices, deleting it from Sylvie after each session.
- The central ethical challenge in healthcare is balancing AI innovation with privacy. Taking ethical considerations of AI into account, Co-Opts is paying careful attention to data sensitivity, consent, algorithmic bias, governance and the risks of re-identification of anonymised data.
- Co-Opts is implementing a human-centred data governance framework alongside technical safeguards like Edge AI for local on-device data processing and federated learning for model improvement, an approach informed by their involvement with *The Turing Way Practitioners Hub*.
- They emphasise engagement with users and experts to develop and strengthen their ethical and data governance framework, including the formation of an anonymisation oversight working group and the active involvement of patients, clinicians, and technology specialists.

Expert in Residence Spotlight: Kevin Flanagan

Kevin Flanagan has a background in both finance and technology, having started as an assembler programmer building online transaction systems. He later spent 14 years in investment banking as an arbitrage trader and senior manager, designing and delivering large global-scale systems. Kevin has managed global development teams and designed systems that process around 30% of global fixed-odds betting. He completed an MSc in Intelligent Systems at UCL and is now working on his

seventh startup, which focuses on digital tools for augmenting mental health treatments for patients and clinicians.

Highlights from *The Turing Way Practitioners Hub*

“I heard about the opportunity to take part in *The Turing Way Practitioners Hub* from Maxine Mackintosh, a colleague at the [One HealthTech](#) community and a previous Practitioners Hub participant. It sounded like an excellent way to speak to people with expertise on the ethics and governance side of things, which we recognised would be crucial to the success of our company and product. We attended a two-day ethics workshop in London, where we met some really interesting people and had some fantastic conversations. The connections we made through the Practitioners Hub have led directly to our exploration of Edge AI with experts at Cardiff University.”

Acknowledgements

This case study is published under [The Turing Way Practitioners Hub 2024-25 Cohort](#) - case study series. The Practitioners Hub is [The Turing Way](#) project that works with experts from partnering organisations to promote data science best practices. In 2024, *The Turing Way* team welcomed **Kevin Flanagan**, founder of Co-Opts, as Experts in Residence to represent interests and opportunities in mental healthcare and EdgeAI. We thank them for their participation in the Practitioners Hub and for leading the development of this case study.

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The Turing Way Practitioners Hub’s 2024-25 Cohort was co-delivered by **Dr Malvika Sharan**, Senior Researcher - Open Research and **Arielle Bennett**, Senior Researcher - Open Source Practices. **Stuart Gillespie** is the technical editor for this case study. **Léllé Demertzi** is the Research Project Manager.

The Turing Way Practitioners Hub, designed and launched in 2023 by Dr Sharan, aims to accelerate the adoption of best practices. Through a six-month cohort-based program, the Hub facilitates knowledge sharing, skill exchange, case study co-creation, and the adoption of open science practices. It also fosters a network of 'Experts in Residence' across partnering organisations.

For any comments, questions or collaboration with *The Turing Way*, please email: .

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